

Studies in Michael Condensation.

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The original intention of the present investigation was to condense fumaric ester with methyl-acetoacetic ester by Michael's method, and thereby to prepare ethyl 1-methyl-4:6-cyclohexadione-1:2-dicarboxylate,

which was to be used as the starting material for a particular line of work. Similar condensations have been done, besides Michael, by other workers (Michael, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1887, **35**, 351; 1891, **43**, 395; 1892, **45**, 55; 1894, **49**, 20); Auwers, *Ber.*, 1891, **24**, 317, 2887; 1893, **26**, 364; 1895, **28**, 263, 1131; *Annalen*, 1896, **292**, 147; Vorländer, *Ber.*, 1894, **27**, 2053; *Annalen*, 1897, **294**, 253; Perkin, *Proc.* 1900, 214; Ruhemann, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1898, **73**, 727, 1006; Hope, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, **401**, 892; Ingold, Shoppee and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **129**, 1477; Ingold and Shoppee, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **129**, 1912). The condensing agent used was sodium, either in the metallic state or as the ethoxide, dry or dissolved in alcohol. In view of the different modifications of the process employed by different workers, it was thought advisable to ascertain the most suitable condition for the production of a compound of the above type before using up the costly and difficultly procurable fumaric ester. Fumaric ester was replaced by its easily available homologue, citraconic ester, and methyl acetoacetic ester by acetoacetic ester. Condensation between these two esters had previously been done by Michael. While repeating his experiment, using, however, the modification adopted by Ruhemann and Cunnington (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1894, **73**, 1006) which is claimed to give very excellent results, we obtained a product different from what Michael had got from the same two

reactants. The result was interesting, and an investigation into the course of the reaction led to conclusions different from Michael's. The interest aroused in the work led to undertaking condensations with other similar substances and kept us confined to Michael's reaction, instead of pursuing the originally planned line.

Condensation between Ethyl Citraconate and Ethyl Acetoacetate.

By the condensation of these two esters with sodium ethoxide in absolute alcoholic solution, Michael obtained a product of the composition, $C_{11}H_{20}O_7$, boiling at 173-174° (26 mm.). Simultaneously there was produced another substance of acidic nature, which however he could not purify and left unstudied. The mechanism of the reaction according to Michael is as follows:

Instead of using an alcoholic medium for the reaction, we used sodium ethoxide dried in vacuum at 180° according to the method of Ruhemann and Cunningham (*loc. cit.*) with the unexpected result that besides a substance of acidic nature, a liquid was obtained distilling at 182° (6 mm.). Analysis showed that it had the same percentage composition as Michael's liquid, *viz.*, $C_{11}H_{20}O_7$. But the two liquids could not possibly be identical as their boiling points were so widely divergent.

The experiment was then repeated according to Michael's original method, and a liquid was obtained distilling at 164° (8 mm.) apparently identical with what Michael had got.

In both these experiments, the major portion of the reaction product was the substance of acidic nature which was a very viscous oil decomposing on heating, before distillation, even at 4 mm. pressure and showing no tendency to solidification. It could be separated from the neutral oil by shaking with sodium carbonate solution. This will be referred to later on.

When the condensation was done in ethereal medium, with "molecular" sodium, a neutral oil was obtained as before with only a very small quantity of the acidic oil. The neutral oil distilled at 180° (5 mm.) and on analysis was found to be $C_{11}H_{20}O_7$, evidently the same as was obtained by the dry ethoxide method. This was proved subsequently, and henceforth served as a method for obtaining the latter in quantity. In the beginning, however, it was examined separately.

Three liquids A, B, C were thus obtained in which A seemed to be identical with C

A—obtained by dry ethoxide method

B— „ „ alcoholate „

C— „ „ , metallic sodium method

All three liquids were submitted to hydrolysis with dilute hydrochloric acid. By a curious coincidence all of them gave acids melting at 119-120°. But whereas a mixture of the acids obtained from A and C did not depress each others melting points, by admixture of either of them with the acid obtained from B the melting point was considerably lowered going down in one case to 93-102° and in other 100-106°. Thus A and C were the same and different from B.

It then appeared to us that the citraconic ester had undergone intramolecular transformation into itaconic ester under the influence of alcoholic alkaline ethoxide (Hope, *loc cit*). On the basis of such an assumption the reaction would be represented as,

Ethyl 8 acetobutane $\alpha\beta\delta$ tricarboxylate

assuming the positive negative rule to hold good. This compound on hydrolysis and splitting off of acetyl group would give butane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ tricarboxylic acid $\text{COOH CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH(COOH)CH}_2\text{COOH}$. The acid is known and has been first prepared by Auwers, and later on by Perkin, Korner and others. The melting point is variously given by different workers as 122°, 116-120°, 109°-111°, 118°-120°. Our substance gave a tribasic acid melting at 119°-120°. This evidence taken in conjunction with the fact that neither α nor β -methyl tricarballylic acid is obtained, tends to support the assumption made.

Further confirmation was sought by preparing a small quantity of itaconic ester itself and condensing it with acetoacetic ester with "molecular" sodium suspended in ether. An oil was obtained distilling at 166° (8 mm) closely agreeing with the temperature of distillation of what has been termed Michael's oil, *viz*, 164° (8 mm). As previously stated the condensation of citraconic ester by the same method gave an oil boiling at 180° (5 mm). This experimental result also supported the assumption that in alcoholic ethoxide medium, citraconic ester was converted into itaconic ester in the

course of condensation, and that in absence of alcohol the ester condensed in the normal fashion even in the presence of sodium ethoxide.

Our assumption was still further corroborated by hydrolysing the oil obtained with itaconic ester. An acid was obtained melting at 118-120°, the melting point remaining unchanged on admixture with the acid obtained from Michael's oil.

The condensation of citraconic ester and acetoacetic ester with sodium ethoxide in alcoholic medium and subsequent hydrolysis were thus proved to proceed as follows:—

Turning now to the other liquid obtained by the dry sodium ethoxide or "molecular" sodium method, this in all probability is a normal condensation product. There are two possible formulae for the liquid $\text{COMe.CH(COOEt).CMe(COOEt)CH}_2\text{.COOEt}$ (I) and $\text{COMe.CH(COOEt).CH(COOEt)CHMe(COOEt)}$ (II). The compound loses CO_2 during hydrolysis. Of the two alternative formulae, formula (I) contains a carboxyl group attached to a tertiary carbon atom, and a compound with this formula has a greater chance of losing CO_2 than the compound with formula (II), and we are therefore justified in adopting formula (I).

Ethyl β -methyl- γ -aceto-propane- $\alpha\beta\gamma$ -tricarboxylate.

β -Methyl- γ -acetopropane- $\alpha\gamma$ -dicarboxylic acid.

The formula for the tricarboxylic ester given above is also in agreement with Michael's rule. In fact this is the formula which Michael ascribed to the liquid previously referred to, which we have proved to possess a different configuration.

With regard to the substances of acidic nature mentioned previously, we assumed them to be ring structures obtained from the open-chain compounds by internal acetoacetic ester condensation.

(Meyer and Jacobsen : "Lehrbuch der organischen Chemie" II, i, p. 817). Thus citraconic ester and acetoacetic ester would give

Ethyl 2-methyl-4 : 5-cyclo-hexadione-1 : 2-dicarboxylate.

The viscous oil obtained from the product of condensation of acetoacetic and citraconic esters (with dry sodium ethoxide or molecular sodium) by shaking with sodium carbonate and subsequent acidification, extraction with ether, drying etc., could not be distilled even at low pressures. Vigorous decomposition ensued and the substance was completely destroyed. It did not solidify after being kept in a vacuum desiccator for about a month. Michael, too, in his experiment met with a similar semi-solid oil and stated that he could not purify or isolate the product. We tried to hydrolyse the substance with acid and alkali of different strengths, but only obtained small quantities of solid mixed with tarry matter which were found to be extremely difficult to purify. The present specimen prepared melted between 190° and 197°. As large quantities of the substance were lost by this process, we took recourse to a different means. The oil was converted into the semicarbazone and this was purified and analysed. The semicarbazone is not formed very readily, but requires three or four hour's heating on the water-bath. But the compound is obtained fairly pure, can easily be further purified and the yield is moderate. Analysis of the compound corresponded to $C_{14}H_{21}N_3O_6$, that is, to the mono-semicarbazone of the β -diketone. The compound melted at 237°.

The ring compound obtained from itaconic ester (or citraconic

ester in alcoholic medium), sodium and acetoacetic ester, would then be formed as follows:—

The semicarbazone of the viscous oil was prepared, and estimation of the nitrogen content showed that it was the mono-semicarbazone of the above ring compound. The melting point is 251°.

Condensation between Fumaric and Aceto acetic Esters.

Condensation between these two esters with sodium-ethoxide had previously been done by Ruhemann and Browning (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1888, 73, 727). They obtained a liquid distilling at 187°—188° (11 mm.). We obtained a light oil and a heavy viscous substance, the former distilling at 145° (4 mm). The divergence between the conditions of distillation of the two liquids at first sight appears to be too great for the liquids to be identical, but this is not surprising when we consider that the same liquid had been prepared in a different way by Emery (*Ber.*, 1890, 23, 3787) who gives the distilling temperature as 175° (9 mm). That is, the fall of boiling point with fall of pressure seems to be abnormally great.

In this case there is no possibility of isomeric conversion, and as a matter of fact the light oils obtained by condensation either with the aid of sodium ethoxide in alcoholic solution or with metallic sodium suspended in ether were the same.

The two products formed in the reaction are:—

The open-chain compound was analysed, and the nitrogen content of the mono-semicarbazone of the ring compound determined. The results were as expected.

Condensation between Ethyl Citraconate and Ethyl Methylacetoacetate.

(a) With sodium ethoxide in alcoholic solution two products were obtained as before and their modes of formation are represented as:—

The open chain compound boils at 175° (9 mm.), and the mono-semicarbazone of the ring compound melts at 247°.

(b) With *dry* sodium ethoxide—the two compounds are represented thus:—

The chain compound boils at 185° (9 mm.) and the mono-semicarbazone of the ring compound melts at 235°.

*Condensation between Ethyl fumarate and
Ethyl Methylacetoacetate.*

The two products obtained are given in the following representation of the reaction:—

The open chain compound boils at 149° (5 mm.), and the mono-semicarbazone of the ring compound melts at 240°.

*Condensation between Ethyl Citraconate
and Ethyl Cyanacetate.*

Perkin and Thorpe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, 75, 52) have effected condensations on similar lines between cyanacetic ester and dimethylacrylic ester and obtained two products, a neutral liquid and an acidic viscous substance which could not be distilled even under diminished pressure. The neutral liquid was the normal condensation product, $\text{CN}.\text{CH}(\text{COOEt}).\text{CMe}_2.\text{CH}_2.\text{COOEt}$ while the acidic oil decomposed on distillation at ordinary pressure losing carbon dioxide and giving a product which they proved conclusively to have the formula, $\text{CN}.\text{CH}_2.\text{CMe}_2.\text{CH}_2.\text{COOEt}$ so that the original acidic liquid, which of course, being in the crude condition, could not be analysed, was given the formula $\text{CN}.\text{CH}(\text{COOH}).\text{CMe}_2.\text{CH}_2.\text{COOEt}$.

Later on, Howles, Thorpe and Udall (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1900, 77, 943) condensed isopropyl acrylic ester with cyanacetic ester and came to similar conclusions. The condensing agent used in both the experiments was sodium ethoxide in alcoholic solution.

Parallel results were obtained with the compounds we used. We got a neutral oil boiling at 170° (5 mm.), and an acidic viscid substance which decomposed on heating into carbon dioxide and a mobile liquid boiling at 286° under ordinary pressure. There was however this difference with Perkin and Thorpe's results that the citraconic ester underwent conversion, as was to be expected, into itaconic ester during the course of condensation. This point was made sure by using finely divided sodium suspended in benzene (ether being rendered unsuitable by the advent of the hot season) as the condensing agent. Following the usual procedure, the reaction yielded only one product, *viz.*, a neutral liquid distilling at 190° (6 mm.), evidently different from the neutral liquid obtained by the former method. The difference was also proved by hydrolysis.

Thus, when alcoholic sodium ethoxide is the condensing agent, the reaction would be represented as :

Ethyl 3-cyano-butane- $\alpha\beta$ -dicarboxylate.

Both A and C gave, after hydrolysis with dilute hydrochloric acid, the same butane $\alpha\beta\gamma$ -tricarboxylic acid also prepared in a different way as stated previously.

The formation of an acid (B) by the condensation of two neutral esters appears to be curious. The explanation advanced by Thorpe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1900, 77, 923) is that the sodium compound of cyanacetic ester reacts in the form— $\text{CN}\cdot\text{CH}:\text{C}(\text{OEt})\cdot\text{ONa}$.

The series of reactions, when the other reactant is dimethyl-acrylic ester, would then be represented as follows :

By using sodium suspended in benzene as the condensing agent, practically one product is formed from citraconic and cyanacetic esters. The acidic product, though formed, is only slight in quantity. The neutral liquid obtained had the same percentage composition as the neutral liquid mentioned just before. This was, of course, according to expectations. The formula for this liquid is $\text{CN}\cdot\text{CH}(\text{COOEt})\cdot\text{CMe}(\text{COOEt})\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{COOEt}$ (ethyl β -methyl- γ -cyanopropene- $\alpha\beta\gamma$ -tricarboxylate.)

On hydrolysis it gave an acid having the percentage composition $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_6$, melting at $160^\circ\text{--}162^\circ$, evidently β -methyl-tricarballic acid (m.p. 164°).

*Condensation between Ethyl Fumarate
and Ethyl Cyanacetate.*

The neutral and acidic products of the reaction have the formulæ given below :

Ethyl γ -cyanopropene- $\alpha\beta\gamma$ tricarboxylate.

and $\text{CN}\cdot\text{CH}(\text{COOH})\cdot\text{CH}(\text{COOEt})\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{COOEt}$ (acidic product).

γ -Cyanopropene- $\alpha\beta\gamma$ -tricarboxylic acid $\alpha\beta$ -diethyl ester.

Hydrolysis with dilute hydrochloric acid yielded an acid melting at 159°-160° which is without doubt tricarballic acid, the accepted melting point of which is 160°-162°.

The neutral oil boiled at 167° (7 mm.) and the acidic compound decomposed on distillation into carbon dioxide and a mobile liquid boiling at 282°. The latter is evidently $\text{CN}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CH}(\text{COOEt})\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{COOEt}$ (ethyl γ -cyano-propane $\alpha\beta$ -dicarboxylate).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of Citraconic Ester.—The method adopted was a slight modification of the process prescribed by Piutti (*Ber.*, 1898, 31, 2039). Citric acid (900 g.) is melted in a wide basin and the molten mass kept at a temperature of 150° for an hour to dehydrate the acid. It is then quickly poured into a one litre distilling flask with a short neck and rapidly distilled over a ring-burner. At first water and carbon dioxide escape, then vigorous decomposition begins with an irritating smell which afterwards becomes more moderate. The liquid distilling over 180° is collected and then redistilled. Citraconic anhydride is obtained distilling at 210°. Yield 110 g.

The citraconic anhydride is esterified with alcohol (700 c.c.) and strong sulphuric acid (70 c.c.). Yield 150 g.

Condensation between Ethyl Citraconate and Ethyl Acetoacetate.

(a) Using dry sodium ethoxide:—

Citraconic ester (18.6 g.), acetoacetic ester (13 g.) and about 2 gm. of finely powdered sodium ethoxide dried in vacuum at 180°, are heated on an oil-bath at about 130° in a flask provided with a reflux tube for about 6 hours. After cooling water is added. An oil is thrown down, but a large portion of the reaction product remains dissolved in water as the sodium compound. A little ice is added and the oil extracted twice with ether. The residual liquid is acidified, when further separation of oil takes place which is also extracted twice with ether. If in the first place no water is added but the reaction mixture is at once acidified and extracted with ether, the ethereal extract contains both the oils which are separated by shaking with sodium carbonate solution. The second or acidic constituent thus removed is recovered by acidification and extraction with

ether. Both the ethereal extracts are dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate, and the ether distilled off. The first product which is a comparatively light oil is the open-chain compound, α -acetyl- β -methyl-tricarballic ester, $\text{MeCO}\cdot\text{CH}(\text{COOEt})\text{CMe}(\text{COOEt})\text{CH}_2\text{COOEt}$, the sodium compound of which is apparently decomposed by water. It is purified by two distillations under diminished pressure when a colourless liquid is obtained distilling constantly at 182° (6 mm). The yield is 10–12 g. (Found: C, 56.87; H, 7.60. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_7$, requires C, 56.96; H, 7.59 per cent.).

The viscous portion of the reaction products weighs about 15 g. It decomposes vigorously on heating even in high vacuum, and hence it could not be distilled.

For the preparation of the semicarbazone it is necessary to heat the mixture of the substance with semicarbazide hydrochloride and sodium acetate for four hours. Crystallised from water. The analytical data shows that it is the mono-semicarbazone of 1-methyl-3:5-cyclohexadione-1:6-dicarboxylic ester. (Found: C, 51.20; H, 6.60; N, 12.61. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_3\text{O}_6$, requires C, 51.37; H, 6.42; N, 12.84 per cent.).

(b) Using sodium ethoxide in alcoholic solution:—

Sodium (4.6 g.) is dissolved in absolute alcohol (50 c.c.) in a round-bottomed flask fitted with a reflux condenser. After cooling acetoacetic ester (26 g.) is added and then citraconic ester (37.2 g.). The mixture is heated on the water-bath for about 8 hours. The flask is cooled and then water added. The two products of the reaction are separated as in the previous case. The neutral ester δ -aceto-butane- $\alpha\beta$ -tricarboxylic ester is obtained in a yield of about 20–25 g., b. p. $164^\circ/8$ mm. (Found: C, 56.75; H, 7.32. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_7$, requires C, 56.96; H, 7.59 per cent.).

Thus the percentage composition is the same as that of the liquid prepared by the dry ethoxide method.

The crude heavy product of the reaction weighs nearly 30 g. The semicarbazone is prepared in the way described before; m. p. 251° . Analysis showed that it is the mono-semicarbazone of the cyclic derivative, 4:6-cyclohexadione-1-carbethoxy-3-acetic acid ethyl ester. (Found: N, 12.55. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_3\text{O}_6$, requires N, 12.84 per cent.).

(c) With metallic sodium in ethereal medium:—

Sodium (2.3 g.) melted under boiling xylene is shaken to a fine powder. After cooling the xylene is replaced by dry ether (75 c.c.).

The reaction is carried out in a stout round-bottomed flask fitted with a reflux condenser. Acetoacetic ester (13 g.) is then added in three or four instalments avoiding elevation of temperature. After about an hour citraconic ester (18.6 g.) is added all at once. The reaction is at first vigorous, but afterwards slows down and is to be kept in progress by carefully warming it on a water-bath. Complete solution of the white particles takes place in 3-4 hours. It is very difficult to start the reaction once it has stopped, and hence from the first spontaneous commencement of the reaction it should be kept going, without allowing the flask to attain room temperature.

The reaction product is decomposed by adding water, when the latter goes into the ethereal layer. This is treated in the usual way. The boiling point of the liquid is 180° (5 mm). The liquid is apparently identical with α -acetyl- β -methyl tricarballic ester prepared by method (a).

Hydrolysis.—The volatile parts of the products obtained by the three methods were submitted to the same process of hydrolysis.

About 10 g. of the tricarboxylic ester are heated on a water-bath with dilute hydrochloric acid (1:2, 75 c. c.) for five hours. The liquid is then directly evaporated as far as possible on the water-bath. The pasty mass solidifies on cooling. The crude solid is then purified by two recrystallisations from a mixture of ethyl acetate and petroleum ether. Yield of the pure product is about 1.5 g. (theoretical yield about 6 g.). The melting point of the pure product in each of the three cases is 10-120°. The acids were mixed, two and two, and melting point of each mixture determined. A mixture of acids from the dry ethoxide method and metallic sodium method showed no change in melting point. But when mixed with the acid obtained by the sodium alcoholate method, the former melted at 98-102° and the latter between 100° and 106°. This proved the identity of the first two acids and their difference from the third.

On hydrolysing α -acetyl- β -methyl-tricarballic ester a dibasic acid of the formula $C_8H_{11}O_6$ is formed. (Found: C, 50.70; H, 6.74. $C_8H_{11}O_6$ requires C, 51.06; H, 6.38 per cent.). On titration with baryta the acid was found to be dibasic. 0.0580 gm. requires 21.1 c.c. of 0.029N baryta. Calculated for a dibasic acid—21.3 c.c. On hydrolysing δ -acetylbutane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylic ester, a tribasic acid of the formula $C_7H_{10}O_6$ is formed. (Found: C, 44.01; H, 5.49. $C_7H_{10}O_6$ requires C, 44.21; H, 5.26 per cent.). On titration with

baryta it was found to be tribasic. 0.0433 g. requires 22.95 c.c. of 0.029 N baryta. Calculated for a tribasic acid—23.43 c.c.

Condensation between Ethyl Fumarate and Ethyl Acetoacetate.

The reaction is carried out in alcoholic solution according to the process given previously. In this case the mixture is heated for five hours instead of eight. Starting with fumaric ester (34.4 g.) about 16 g. of pure open-chain compound are obtained and nearly 30 g. of the crude ring compound. The boiling point of the former is 145° (4 mm.). The same product, viz., α -acetyltricarballic ester is also obtained by conducting the condensation in ethereal medium with molecular sodium.

The *open-chain* compound. (Found: C, 55.02; H, 7.32. $C_{14}H_{22}O_7$, requires C, 55.21; H, 7.52 per cent.).

The *ring* compound: (Found: N, 13.55. $C_{13}H_{18}O_6$, N₂, requires N, 13.41 per cent.).

Condensation between Ethyl Citraconate and Ethyl Methylacetoacetate.

The procedure employed either when the reaction is done in an alcoholic medium or with dry sodium ethoxide is as described before except that the duration of heating is prolonged to twelve hours in both cases. Starting with citraconic ester (18.6 g.) the yield of the open-chain compound in the first case is 15.5 g. (b. p. 175°/9 mm.) and in the second it is about 12 g. (b. p. 185°/9 mm.).

The analytical results are as follows:—

(a) Alcoholate method—

(i) *Open-chain* compound. (Found: C, 57.97; H, 8.00. $C_{14}H_{22}O_7$, requires C, 58.18; H, 7.87 per cent.).

(ii) *Semicarbazone* of the ring structure, m.p. 247°. (Found: N, 12.18. $C_{13}H_{18}N_2O_6$, requires N, 12.31 per cent.).

(b) The corresponding analytical results for the products obtained by the dry sodium ethoxide method are:

(i) *Open-chain* compound. (Found: C, 58.00; H, 8.11 per cent.).

(ii) *Semicarbazone*, m.p. 235°. (Found: N, 12.16 per cent.). The theoretical figures are the same as in (a).

Condensation between Ethyl fumarate and Ethyl Methylacetoacetate.

The duration of heating is about 8 hours, and 17.2 g. of fumaric ester gave 12 g. of the neutral condensation product. The boiling

point is 149° (5 mm.). (Found: C, 56.72; H, 7.73. $C_{11}H_{11}O_7$, requires C, 56.96; H, 7.59 per cent.).

Mono-semicarbazone of the ring compound melts at 240°. (Found: N, 12.60. $C_{11}H_{11}N_3O_6$, requires N, 12.84 per cent.).

Condensation between Ethyl Citraconate and Ethyl Cyanacetate.

(a) *In alcoholic medium*:—

Sodium (2.3 g.) is dissolved in absolute alcohol (25 c.c.) and citraconic ester (11.3 g.) added in three or four portions to avoid too much elevation of temperature. The white crystalline sodio-cyana-cetic ester forms almost a cake within the reaction flask. Citraconic ester (18.6 g.) is then added and the mixture heated on the water-bath for 7-8 hours, cooled, acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid, and then extracted with ether. The ethereal layer contains two products from which the acidic constituent is separated by shaking with alkaline carbonate solution. It is reprecipitated by acid and extracted with ether. The two ethereal extracts are dried and freed from ether. The neutral ester is purified by distillation under diminished pressure (b.p. 170°/5 mm.). Yield—10 gms. The acidic viscous liquid cannot be distilled without decomposition. It is heated at ordinary pressure whereby CO_2 escapes, as can be readily tested by lime water, and a light liquid is obtained which distills at 286°, under atmospheric pressure. Yield—10 gms. (Found: (neutral liquid) C, 55.32; H, 7.30; N, 4.48. $C_{14}H_{21}O_6N$ requires C, 56.19; H, 7.02; N, 4.68 per cent.).

Analysis of the second liquid.—(Found: C, 55.90; H, 7.61; N, 6.00. $C_{11}H_{11}O_6N$ requires C, 56.15; H, 7.49; N, 6.17 per cent.).

(b) *In benzene medium*.—The reaction is carried out in the same way as when ether was used in some of the experiments described previously, with this difference that it was done on a water-bath. Citraconic ester (18.6 g.) gave about 30 g. of a liquid distilling at 190°/6 mm. (Found N, 4.52. $C_{14}H_{21}O_6N$ requires N, 4.68 per cent.).

Hydrolysis:—The three liquids thus obtained by the two methods were hydrolysed with dilute hydrochloric acid. Ten g. of the liquid were heated on the water-bath with 70 c.c. of dilute HCl (1:1) for six hours. Ammonium chloride and a nitrogen-free acid are formed in each case. The liquid is evaporated to a small volume, cooled and

extracted with ether. On evaporation of the ether, a solid remains which may be recrystallised from ethyl acetate and a little ligroin. The yield is very small, about 0.5 g. in each case, owing to the difficulty of extracting them from water in which they are extremely soluble. The acids obtained from the first two liquids melted at 118-120° and were proved identical with butane $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylic acid prepared as stated before by a different method, by mixed melting point method. The acid from the third liquid melted at 160-162°. This is β -methyl tricarballic acid whose m.p. is given as 164°.

Condensation between Ethyl Fumarate and Ethyl Cyanacetate.

The experimental procedure is the same as in the last experiment. The reaction is carried out in alcoholic solution. Two products were obtained as before, the neutral liquid boiling at 167° under 7 mm. and the acidic portion decomposed on heating, evolving CO₂ and giving a liquid of b.p. 282°. The yields from 17.2 g. of fumaric ester were respectively 12.5 g. and 11 g. when the heating was for 6 hours. (Found (neutral liquid): N, 4.70. C₁₁H₁₆O₈ N requires N, 4.91 per cent.).

Product obtained from acid liquid: (Found: N, 6.32. C₁₀H₁₅O₄N requires N, 6.57 per cent.).